

THE EFFECT OF THERMAL EXPOSURE ON THE FRACTURE AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF C/Al COMPOSITES

Sui Quanwu, Guo Shuqi, Tang Fengjin and Wang Ninghuan
Institute of Metal Research, Academia Sinica, Shenyang 110015, China

ABSTRACT

C/Al and Gr/Al precursors are exposed to difference temperature and time to study the effect of thermal exposure on the tensile strength and fracture. The results shown that the strength of C/Al precursor is increased 20% when the temperature of thermal exposure is 723K for 2hr.

The C/Al composites are produced by lower temperature diffusion bonding. Thermal exposure and cycle to difference temperature and time lead to the strength occur some change. After thermal exposure at 723K for 3hr. the strength of C/Al composite is improved 15% more than the fabrication condition. This paper also studies fracture behavior and points out a good interface is not necessarily a strong interface.

Key Words: Ultrasonic infiltration, Thermal exposure, Composite, Interface, Fracture.

1. INTRODUCTION

Graphite or carbon fibers resist wetting when immersed in most molten metals. Before eighty various methods have been investigated in order to fabricate metal-matrix composites to improving the bonding between the fiber and matrix providing a coating of interface diffusion barrier.

In 1976, Amateau^[1] was emphasisesly suggested that CVD Ti-B coating is a better method. But recently, the method is incompletely satisfactory. I think it has two reasons, the first is that the technology of the method is complex and the efficiencies is lower, and the composite part fabricated is difficult. The second is a lot of cholorion presented on the interface and it is very severe defect for the structure composite so that after eighty some new methods are occurred. Richer et al^[2] suggest a surface treatment with aqueous solutions of K_2ZrF_6 has been carried out to improve, in dramatic manner, the wetting of carbon (or SiC)-base ceramics by liquid light alloys at low temperature. K_2ZrF_6 surface treatment appears to be particularly suitable for processing composite materials made of carbon (or SiC) fibers preforms and aluminum-base matrices according to techniques directly derived from the light alloy.

Cornie et al ^[3] applied pressure infiltration processing of graphite fiber reinforced aluminum alloys directly to manufacture Gr/Al composite. The method is very simple and effective. The strength of Gr/Al composite is more than 700 MPa.

H.A. Katzman^[4] presented a fiber coatings for composite fabrication. In this paper he shown that graphite fibers resist wetting, in order to fabricate metal-matrix composites, the fibers must be coated with a material to both facilitate wetting by the metal and protect the fibers against chemical degradation during processing and subsequent use. In these coatings except B-Ti coating they pointed the methods are chiefly solution coating process to improving the wetting between the fiber and matrix. In this paper they reported the ultrasonic vibration method is expected to be come a valuable technique to enhance wetting of fibers with various metals. But in this method the fiber surface is coated with the boron-silicon oxide coating has been found to provide complete infiltration of the alloy melt into the fiberbundle. Few years ago we studied an ultrasonic liquid metal infiltration to produce Gr/Al or C/Al precursors without any coating on the fiber surface.

The method is more simple and effective. The equipment is first shown in this paper, C/Al and Gr/Al precursors are exposed to difference temperature and time to study the effect of thermal exposure on the strength and fracture. In order to reduce the reaction between the fiber and matrix and the fiber degradation the C/Al composite is fabricated br lower temperature diffusion bonding. C/Al composites are exposed to difference temperature and time to study the change of the composite strength and fracture in order to find the proper bonding between the fiber and matrix, the precursor and precursor. The result just as Cornie^[5] pointed that a good interface is not necessary a strong interface for continuously fiber reinforced composites.

2. EXPERIMENT

2.1 Fabrication of C/Al and Gr/Al precursor

The ultrasonic liquid metal infiltration is employed to manufacture C/Al and Gr/Al precursors without any coating on the fiber surface. Which is directly to achieve wettability between the fiber and matrix. The equipment of C/Al and Gr/Al precursors fabricated shown in Fig.1. It consists of three parts. The first is the ultrasonic-producer and the energy-translater. The second is the molten metal bath and furnace. The third is the supply fiber spool and the winding precursor reel.

The fiber bundle is continuously drown through a bath containing molten 1100 aluminum which is over 30-50K of aluminum melting point. The liquid aluminum is fully infiltration into the fiber bundle by ultrasonic vibration and C/Al or Gr/Al precursor is winded on the reel.

2.2 Manufacture of C/Al composite

In order to reduce the interface reaction between the fiber and matrix, the low temperature diffusion bonding is applied to produce C/Al composite. The temperature of the diffusion bonding is 750K-760K. The pressure is 60MPa and the constant pressure time is 30 min. The size of the composite sheet is 150x65x2 mm and the specimen of C/Al is cuted to 150x6x2 mm which is provided to measure the strength and thermal exposure test.

2.3. Thermal exposure and the strength measurement

In order to study the effect of thermal exposure and cool and thermal cycle on the tensile strength, C/Al and Gr/Al precursors ad C/Al composite are exposed to difference temperature and time. C/Al and Gr/Al precursors are exposed from 723K to 973K for 2hr. and its are cycled

by cool and thermal between 823K and 273K for 100 times. C/Al composites are respectively exposed to 723K, 763K and 793K for 3hr, and it is cycled by cool and thermal between 293K and 753K for 25 times. The tensile strength of the specimens are also measured after treatmenting.

2.4. The fracture observation

The fracture of these composites were observed after tensile test by scanning electron microscope and found the fracture morphology relation to the treatment technology.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 shown the equipment of C/Al and Gr/Al precursor fabricated. The strength and modulus of C/Al and Gr/Al precursor were determined. As fabrication condition C/Al precursor is 1000MPa and 131 GPa, Gr/Al precursor is 900 MPa and 184 GPa which arrived ROM values. It explains that the method is very effective although without diffusion barrier coating on the fiber surface^[6]. Fig.2 shown the effect of thermal exposure on the tensile strength of C/Al and Gr/Al precursors from 723K to 973K for 2hr. The tensile strength has some increasing when the temperature is lower than 823K. The strength of C/Al precursor is increased 20% more than the fabrication condition when the temperature of thermal exposure is 723K. The phenomenon appears that the stress between the fiber and matrix is reduced by improving the interface bonding. The interface reaction is not severe when the temperature of thermal exposure is lower than 823K for 2hr.

Fig.3 shown the effect of cool and thermal cycle on the tensile strength of C/Al and Gr/Al precursors from 823K to 273K. The strength of C/Al precursor is linear reducing with the increasing of the cycle time. But the tensile strength of Gr/Al precursor is increased before 30 cycles and the strength is lower than the fabrication condition after 60 cycles. Which explains that the thermal stability and stiffness of the graphite fiber are better than the carbon fiber.

Generally speaking, the hot pressure temperature of C/Al and Gr/Al composite fabricated are employed at 823K to 853K for diffusion bonding. In this paper the lower temperature (750K) hot pressure is applied to manufacture C/Al composite for reducing the interface reaction and using pressure is 60 MPa.

Fig.4 shown the effect of thermal exposure on the tensile strength of C/Al composite. From Fig.4 we can see the tensile strength is 292.5 MPa as the fabrication condition. After thermal exposure to 723K for 3hr. the strength of C/Al composite is increased to 346 MPa which improves more 15% than the fabrication condition. When the thermal exposure temperature is 763K the strength just as the fabrication condition. If the thermal exposure temperature is more than 773K, the strength will be lower than the fabrication condition and it explains that the interface reaction occurred and Al_4C_3 is produced at the interface.

Fig.5 shown the tensile fracture of C/Al composite as fabrication condition which appears that the bonding between of the precursor is very closer and the interface bonding is very strong, the fracture exhibits a brittle so the strength is lower.

Fig.6 shown the fracture of C/Al composite after thermal exposure at 723K for 3hr, which shown the bonding between of the precursors had some improving and the fracture morphology presented some toughness, the precursors appeared a little shrink. When the temperature of thermal exposure was increased to 763K for 3hr, the fracture exhibited some toughness as Fig.7 shown. If the temperature of thermal exposure was increased to 793K for 3hr. the strength of

C/Al composite reduced to 263MPa which is lower 10% than the fabrication condition and the fracture appears a brittle as Fig.8 shown and Al_4C_3 products occur at the interface between the carbon fiber and matrix.

In Fig.2 the strength of C/Al precursor occurred reducing after 873K of thermal exposure for 2hr, but in Fig.8 C/Al composite was exposed to 793K the strength shown reducing which explains that the stress of hot pressure can increase the reaction between the fiber and matrix during the thermal exposure process.

Fig.9 shown the fracture of cool and thermal cycle between 293K and 753K for 25 times. the bonding between of the precursors occurred some improving than the fabrication condition as Fig.5 shown so the strength increased 10% more than the fabrication condition.

These studies explain that the strength and fracture depend upon the experience of the manufacture and treatment.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The equipment of the ultrasonic liquid metal infiltration is effectively employed to manufacture C/Al and Gr/Al precursors although without diffusion barrier coating on the fiber surface and the performances are not lower than the other methods.
2. The tensile strength of C/Al and Gr/Al precursor are not lower than the fabrication condition before thermal exposure to 823K for 2hr. The tensile strength of Gr/Al precursor is increased when the cycles less than 30 times between 823K and 273K.
3. The strength of C/Al composite fabricated by low temperature hot pressure is lower and the fracture is brittle. A proper thermal exposure and cool and thermal cycle can increase the strength of C/Al composite and improving the interface bonding between the precursors.
4. We also can conclude that for continuously fiber reinforced composites, a good interface is not necessarily a strong interface.

References

1. M.F.Amateau., Progress in the Development of Graphite Aluminum Composites Using Liquid Infiltration Technology. J. of Composite Materials October 1976, Vol.10, pp279-296.
2. J. P.ROCHER, J.M.QUENISSET, R.NASLAIN., Wetting improvement of Carbon or Silicon Carbide by aluminum alloys based on a K_2ZrF_6 surface treatment: application to composite material coating J. of Materials Science 24(1989)pp2697-2703.
3. J.A. Cornie, G-D Zhang, Q.Li, S-Y Zhang, B.Kowing and J.T.blucher., Pressure Infiltration Processing of P-55 (Graphite) Fiber Reinforced Aluminum Alloys. "Symposium on composites-processing, Microstructure & Properties" 2nd International ceramic Science and Technology Congress of the American Ceramic Society, Orlando, FL, Nov 13-15, 1990.
4. H.A.Katzman., Fiber coating for Composite Fabrication Materials & Manufacturing Processes, 5(1)pp1-15(1990).
5. J.A. Cornie, Designing Interfaces MRS Bulletin/April 1991, Vol. XVI, No.4, pp27-28.
6. Sui Quanwu et al; The Interface Structure in C/Al Composite Without any Coating, ICCM VII Vol. PP458-462, 1989.

Fig.1 The ultrasonic liquid in filtration equipment

1. power source 2. Cable 3. Supply fiber spool 4. Direction reel 5. Molten metal bath
 6. Furnace 7. Energy translator 8. Thermocouple 9. Control panel 10. Winding precursor reel

Fig.2 The effect of thermal exposure on the tensile strength of C/Al and Gr/Al precursor from 723K to 973K for 2hr.

Fig.3 The effect of cool and thermal cycle on the tensile strength of C/Al and Gr/Al precursor from 823K to 273K.

Fig.4 The effect of thermal exposure on the tensile strength of C/Al composite.

Fig.5 The tensile fracture of C/Al composite as fabrication condition

Fig.6 The tensile fracture of C/Al composite after thermal exposure to 723K for 3hr.

Fig.7 The tensile strength of C/Al composite after thermal exposure to 793K for 3hr.

Fig.8 The tensile fracture of C/Al composite after thermal exposure to 793K for 3hr.

Fig.9 The tensile fracture of C/Al composite after cool and thermal cycle between 293K and 753K for 25 times.